

Poster 19* : Dynamics of RNA viruses in *Leishmania* spp

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To better understand virus-host interactions, it is essential to analyze viral load dynamics in parasitic protists. In this study, we monitored the viral loads of three RNA viruses—LRV1, LRV2, and LBV—in three *Leishmania* species: *L. guyanensis*, *L. major*, and *L. braziliensis*, respectively. Daily measurement of viral load was conducted by RT-qPCR, normalized for parasite density. All virus-species combinations exhibited a comparable temporal pattern: viral levels increased during the early logarithmic phase, peaked in the late logarithmic to early stationary phase, and then dropped. This signifies a controlled connection between viral replication and host cell physiology, possibly linked to changes in host metabolism, replication rates, or immune evasion strategies. The findings provide crucial understanding of endosymbiotic virus regulation in *Leishmania*, potentially aiding future studies on virus effects on parasite virulence.

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